

EARTH SCIENCES

COUINTERACTIN THE SHARP RISE OF THE WORLD OCEAN

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Abstract

Global warming on the planet, has dramatically affected the melting of the polar caps, giving an increase in the water level of the world's oceans. In this regard, NT in the scientific environment, there have been quite a lot of scientific disputes and polemics, which do not always give a full scientific understanding of the state of affairs with climate change on the planet. At times, instead of deep analysis of the occurring climatic phenomena, we see substitution of the basis of the phenomena with predictions and scientific beliefs.

Rising sea levels are a serious consequence of climate change. Haiti, the Maldives and other island nations are threatened with extinction. In the past few decades, the ocean has begun to warm almost 40% faster than it did back in the middle of the last century, and water levels are rising at an accelerated rate. Here the opinions of scientists are bifurcated, some believe that the heating of the planet to a greater extent depends on cosmic radiation, which has increased dramatically over the last century, others prove the concept of saturation of the earth's atmosphere with carbon dioxide CO₂, pollution of the world's oceans with plastic, which is a multilayered ball, covers the bottom and does not allow to cool magma enveloping the core of the earth, which in turn in the process of overheating increases in volume and rises to the upper layers of the earth. Third groups of scientists tend to consider the first two concepts as equally existing and actively influencing global warming.

Any scientific debate must determine with sufficient precision the timing of the impending catastrophe. Here there are very large discrepancies, they are measured from ten to a hundred years, everyone uses their own dynamics of events, which does not allow the heads of state and their government to specify their actions in the Program documents on environmental protection of their states.

It is time to abandon the boundaries of ecological disasters, it is impossible to protect oneself in full measure with state borders, the world ocean and airspace unites all countries and states.

Keywords: Polar caps, magma, flooding, global warming, environmental protection.

Problem Statement. To date, the average level of the world's oceans has risen by about 21 cm since 1900, with an immediate increase of 7.5 cm over the last 25 years. Each year the water level rises by 3.2 mm. These seem like minuscule values, but the rate at which sea levels are changing today is 2.5 times faster than it was just a decade ago.

Analyzing recent studies and publications. Klige R.K., Zakharov V.G. Changes in the snow-ice regime of Antarctica // *Modern Global Changes in the Natural Environment*. - Moscow: Scientific World, 2006. C. 577-606. In this paper a group of scientists gives a detailed analysis of the inevitable melting of the Antarctic ice cover, which gives a significant rise in the level of the World Ocean, disturbing the natural equilibrium of the entire continent. In the works of Ukrainian scientists: <https://www.rbc.ua/Bepa/Balabukh>: Ukraine will be resettled "climate refugees" from Africa and Asia 2024, P. 8. The work gives an overview of floods in many countries and continents, which will lead to a population explosion with the resettlement of large numbers of people in Ukraine. Ego Chelokian Professor at the University of Massachusetts https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vS_Qi_T6KAbM Address to the three presidents: Russian Federation, USA, China. He makes strong arguments about the impending catastrophe of planetary scale in a very short period of time - two decades.

The last researches of the European and scientists and the USA, have defined earlier unknown regularity of overheating of magma and a core of a planet at the expense of an additional source of energy from space

that leads to overheating of waters of the World Ocean and awakening of sleeping volcanoes of a planet.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

The general unsolved problem included the issues of curbing emissions of the greenhouse gas CO₂, which China and the USA had previously completely rejected. These countries refused to fulfil the decisions of the International Paris Conference, but subsequently accepted the decisions and signed an agreement. Later, the International Conference in Glasgow summarised the results of seven years of work of all states and assessed many countries in solving the impending global ecological catastrophe.

Purpose of the article. (The purpose of your research ...). Our group of scientists from the Danube Institute of the NU Odessa Maritime Academy has been working on the issues of ecology and climate change for ten years. The Institute's team has been awarded a number of International Environmental Grants. The latest Ukraine-Turkey-Romania International Grant is dedicated to the protection of the Black Sea coast from flooding. It is a large joint analytical and research work for two years.

Outline of the main material. Global flooding will affect up to 250 million people and even the most civilised countries will be under water. The rate of sea level rise has more than doubled, from 1.4 millimetres per year for most of the 20th century to 3.6 millimetres per year between 2006 and 2015. This is caused, among other things, by the melting of Greenland's glaciers. The NASA mission carefully studied the Greenland

coastline and found that the glaciers are melting six or seven times faster than they did just 25 years ago, if the entire Greenland ice sheet were to melt, global sea levels would rise by about 7.4 metres. Data collected by the OMG mission shows that glaciers are at greater risk than anyone knew and are melting two to four times faster than previously thought, writes Scitech Daily.

In the course of the study, the mission's aircraft flew over Greenland a kilometre that would have taken it around the globe more than 13 times. Observations from space did not allow us to understand how fast the ice is melting: the upper layers are melting relatively slowly, but deeper the ocean is getting warmer and saltier. The latest study shows that deep down, the glacier is being eaten away by warmer water, losing ice four to five times faster than at the surface. It turned out that about a third of Greenland's glaciers are gradually descending into warmer water - they account for half of the mainland's ice loss. The rise in ocean level by 7.4 metres is not just a fact, but a harbinger of a worldwide catastrophe. Scientists have even drawn up a map showing (in red) which areas will be flooded if sea levels rise by 6 metres.

At the moment, every tenth person on the planet lives in a region less than 10 metres above sea level. A rise in global sea level of even 1 metre could result in severe floods and tsunamis that would wipe out island nations and coastal cities. For example, London is 11 metres above sea level, while St. Petersburg is only 1 metre above sea level. This means that it will go under water at the very beginning. Countries such as Bangladesh and the Netherlands are at risk of flooding. Rise of the level by 20 cm will make 740 thousand people in Nigeria homeless, and Tuvalu will simply go under water, writes Wikipedia. As for Ukraine, we are not threatened with serious flooding in the next 100 years. The

average height of the plain part is 175 metres above sea level, Kiev is at the level of 179 metres. The lowest among regional centres is Kherson (50 metres) and Ivano-Frankivsk (343 metres). However, the current beaches of the Azov Sea may suffer or even disappear. The lowest land area in Crimea is 0.41 metres below sea level.

The World Meteorological Organisation has recognised 2023 as the hottest year on record. Temperature increases have been regularly recorded over the past decades. Compared to pre-industrial levels, the average temperature on the planet has risen by 1.4 degrees Celsius.

Scientists recognise that the main cause of these changes is human activity. Air temperature is an important indicator of changes in the state of the entire climate system:

atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, lithosphere and finally the biosphere, including humans and their activities. Like changes in human body temperature, it signals that something is wrong with the planet. The last time global temperatures exceeded the average pre-industrial temperature by 0.5-1.5 degrees on the planet was 125,000 years ago. In the last half-century, the rise in air temperature has been the most intense in 2,000 years. Such temperature, which was observed on the planet in 2023, was almost 100 thousand years ago. It is human activity that is the cause of these changes. This conclusion was reached by scientists in the sixth report of the Intergovernmental Experts on Climate Change. It should be noted that not only the temperature of the atmosphere, but also the ocean and the Earth's surface are significantly increasing. And this leads to a rapid change in all components of the climate system [1].

Fig. 1. Ukrainian polar explorers show summer in Antarctica.

The further increase in air temperature will continue to determine the change of seasons: the duration of summer will increase and winter will decrease. Such trends are characteristic of all scenarios, but the intensity of these changes may be different depending on the scenario. Thus, in the next 20 years the duration of summer in the vast majority of the territory of Ukraine may increase by a week, in another scenario - by two weeks compared to the beginning of the century. In the middle of the century summer may last two or three weeks longer and almost a month under another scenario. By the end of the XXI century, the duration of summer will be almost the same as in the middle of the century. But under another scenario, changes in the duration of summer may be unprecedented in Ukraine compared to 1991-2010: from one month in the east of the country to two months or more in the Carpathians and Crimea [2].

We will no longer be able to stop climate change. It is important now to prevent the increase in global temperature by two degrees, and even better - to limit its growth to 1.5 degrees. However, as early as 2023, the annual average global temperature was already 1.5 degrees above pre-industrial temperatures. According to the WMO, these changes could exceed these figures in the next five years. Since the main cause of the substantial increase in air temperature is human activity, a substantial increase in greenhouse gas emissions and an intensification of the greenhouse effect, it is necessary to reduce the concentration of greenhouse gases. This can be achieved in two ways: by increasing the energy efficiency of technologies and by promoting energy conservation. However, given the scale of the changes taking place, it is clear that these measures are no longer sufficient. It is necessary to adapt to the new conditions that are now emerging in order to prevent significant economic damage and preserve life on the planet.

Protecting the coasts of the world's oceans is one of the most urgent and challenging tasks of our time. In this context, scientists from the Danube Institute and their colleagues from Turkey and Romania have identified ways of working together to protect the Black Sea coast from flooding. The difficulty lies in the fact that the huge water resources from the rising water will have to be transferred to higher levels from the level of the World Ocean, which is sea water that cannot be used for irrigation and direct human consumption. Heavy-duty desalination plants will be needed. Artificial saline lakes themselves should be used for breeding of valuable fish species and desalination of water. It will be impossible to do without damming of the coast and large volumes of dredging works for accumulation of incoming water.

At this time of disunity of the world community and military actions in many countries, it will be almost impossible to ensure unity of action in the fight against the elements. The appeal of Professor Ego Chelokyan to the Heads of World States to stop wars and unite all forces and resources for the benefit of preserving life on our planet is still unanswered. It is difficult to accept Ego Chelokyan's information about the destruction of humanity in 10 years, although the author of the article has a hypothesis about the change in the forces applied to the surface of the planet due to the rapid melting of the polar caps [3]. It is enough to assume that the melting of ice in the northern and southern hemispheres will change the forces applied to the earth's surface: if we take only the coriolis forces, they will change due to the melting of the polar caps. Most of the water in the polar caps will move to the equator, changing the centrifugal force of the earth's rotation, which may lead to a change in the position of the earth's rotation axis [4].

Fig. 2. Location of forces during the Earth's rotation

R is the radial force, V is the velocity vector along the Earth's meridian, F is the Coriolis force along the Earth's meridian.

According to Harvard University scientists, further displacement of the earth's core will occur, and this may happen in 5 years, which will lead to the death of entire states such as India and China. Scandinavian countries will go under water. The US will be flooded by half of its area, the entire Black Sea coast, the mouth of the Danube River, Western Siberia of the Russian

Federation will turn into a lifeless desert, and it is difficult to predict the full extent of the disaster.

Conclusions and proposals. Mankind is on the threshold of its destruction, not realising that militaristic values and globalist aspirations will not be needed. It is impossible to divide the world and to protect mankind from the planetary catastrophe in a single state,

only unity around the universal disaster of scientific forces, financial resources, all mankind, will allow to save the planet and the life of all living things. Undoubtedly, we cannot do without solving technical questions related to climate collapse on the basis of high-tech technologies.

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